

Richardson, D.M., Foxcroft, L.C., Latombe, G., Le Maitre, D.C., Rouget, M. & Wilson, J.R.U. (2020). The biogeography of South African terrestrial plant invasions. In: Van Wilgen, B.W., Measey, J. Richardson, D.M., Wilson, J.R.U. & G.J., Zengeya, T. (eds). Biological invasions in South Africa. Springer, Berlin. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-32394-3_3

Supplementary Appendixes 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4

Supplementary Appendix 3.2 Drawing conclusions from two national-scale assessments of alien plants in South Africa

Versfeld et al. (1998) reported on a rapid reconnaissance of the extent of alien plant invasions (largely woody plant taxa) in South Africa undertaken largely in 1996-1997. This assessment (hereafter “Versfeld”) combined expert workshop outputs, existing mapped data and detailed field mapping.

A second national-scale assessment of the extent of alien plant invasions is the National Alien Invasive Plant Survey of the Agricultural Research Council which was done mainly during 2007 (Kotzé et al., 2010). This survey (hereafter “NIAPS”) focussed on invasive species (mainly trees and shrubs) that are targeted for control by the Working for Water programme and it excluded a very large proportion of arid South Africa.

The issues of accuracy and completeness of these two historical datasets on invasions at the national level have been well documented (Le Maitre et al., 2013; van Wilgen et al., 2012; Versfeld et al., 1998). These challenges, combined with the different methods used for the mapping means that the two datasets cannot easily be compared to estimate the change in the extent and density of invasions between these two surveys. One of the notable inconsistencies was that the NIAPS data indicated a substantial decline in the wattles in the fynbos biome (van Wilgen et al., 2012), which is unlikely because Working for Water was not treating a large enough area of wattles to make such a difference possible (van Wilgen et al., 2017), and biological control was not very effective at that stage (Impson et al., 2008). Here, we compare the two datasets as carefully as possible, taking account of inconsistencies, to determine whether any inferences can be made about changes in the extent and density of invasions in the period between the two surveys. We first comment on key features of the two surveys.

Versfeld data

Overestimation of invasions was a problem in some parts of the Versfeld dataset because parts of the areas mapped and described as invaded by experts included very extensive polygons with densities of invasions $\leq 1\%$ canopy cover (Versfeld et al., 1998). This was done mainly as a precautionary measure when experts knew that invasive species were present in an area but could not estimate densities. Many of these large polygons included areas that

were transformed based on the 1996 land cover. A test was done to determine how much this potential overestimation could influence the assessment of total invaded areas and the condensed hectares. The differences in areas were typically less than 5% which means that this correction does not explain the inconsistencies. The sampling intensity in the NIAPS survey (Kotzé et al., 2010) is such that the probability of detecting invasions of $\leq 1\%$ is low so it is likely that the extent of these invasions would be under-reported. This possibility was tested by summarising the data for key species by density class to assess the influence of removing the lower density classes.

NIAPS

The NIAPS landscape invasion mapping process states excluded “arid bioregions” of South Africa from the aerial surveys of the homogeneous mapping units (HMUs) although HMUs were defined for the entire country. This means that Desert, Nama Karoo and Succulent Karoo Biomes were excluded, as were arid parts of the Grassland and Savanna Biomes. All the azonal types (e.g. floodplain wetlands, salt pans) within the mapped areas were included. However, a strip of the Succulent Karoo along the Namaqualand coast as far north as the Orange River and inland to include the western part of the desert biome was included in the mapping (Ian Kotze pers. comm. Jan. 2019). In total, the HMUs of the NIAPS that were mapped in South Africa, excluding the areas that were classified as transformed in the 2000 land cover, comes to $\pm 44\,313\,800$ ha or 32.4% of South Africa. The area of the HMUs where invasions were detected is $\pm 18\,012\,419$ ha so invasions were observed in about 40.6% of the surveyed area.

Matching Versfeld and NIAPS

A dataset of the arid bioregions used in the NIAPS study was obtained from Ian Kotze and used to select only the Versfeld polygons (and parts of polygons) that overlapped with the areas included in the NIAPS survey. The resulting polygon data was then summarised to get the areas mapped for the Versfeld survey which were also covered by the NIAPS.

The total area mapped by Versfeld within the NIAPS mapping domain is 6 102 683 ha and the condensed area of the invasions in these polygons is 963 058 ha. The total area mapped by Versfeld was 10 076 365 ha and the condensed area was 1 736 438 ha. This means that the Versfeld mapping included an additional 3.97 million ha with a condensed invaded area

of 0.73 million ha, mainly extensive invasions by *Prosopis* (mesquite), Cactaceae (cacti) and other invaders in the in the arid bioregions. In contrast, the total area of the homogenous mapped units where an invading species was recorded during the NIAPS is 18 020 188 ha and the condensed invaded area was 1 483 692 ha. This means that the NIAPS recorded invasions over more than three times the area that was mapped by Versfeld and recorded a much greater condensed invaded area.

A comparison of the data for the overlapping areas shows that there are some very large discrepancies between the two surveys in both the total and the condensed areas invaded (Suppl. Table 3.2.1) for most of the NIAPS taxa. Among the *Acacia* species, *A. cyclops* and *A. saligna* stand out as having 2-4 times greater invaded areas and condensed areas in the Versfeld dataset than in the NIAPS, with the wattles showing the reverse. Data for pines (condensed area) and eucalypts are markedly different and, although pines are known to be increasing in extent and density, the differences recorded are confounded by the more extensive sampling by the NIAPS. A comparison of the maps shows that one of the key reasons for this was the much more comprehensive coverage of the Eastern Cape, where there are very extensive and dense invasions of wattles that were not captured in the Versfeld dataset. Another factor that has played a role is the visibility of some species from the air. *Lantana camara*, *Biancaea decapetala* and *Solanum mauritianum* often occur under other species or along woody-grass ecotones where they are less likely to be detected by the NIAPS.

Suppl. Table 3.2.1 Matched Versfeld data for NIAPS species groups and single species with the comparison confined to the areas mapped by the NIAPS. The total area mapped by the NIAPS is the area of the homogenous mapping units where the species was recorded which is an estimate of the total invaded area. “*Acacia saligna*” includes *A. pycnantha*; Versfeld “wattle” includes *Acacia* spp., *A. dealbata*, *A. decurrens* and *A. mearnsii* to match the NIAPS taxon. *Rosa rubiginosa* was not recorded in the Versfeld surveys but several other species in the Rosaceae were. Italics indicate where the Versfeld area divided by the NIAPS area is >2.0 or <0.5.

Taxon	Versfeld data 1995-1996		NIAPS data 2007	
	Total ha	Condensed ha	Total ha ¹	Condensed ha
<i>Acacia cyclops</i>	1 357 810	269 579	763 963	55 758

<i>Acacia melanoxylon</i>	766 957	4 623	97 606	2 728
<i>Acacia saligna</i>	1 088 010	73 284	444 169	50 720
Wattles (<i>Acacia</i> spp.)	1 647 238	164 649	7 475 944	470 588
<i>Agave</i> spp.	489 376	12 258	875 813	11 277
<i>Arundo donax</i>	135 939	2 353	156 731	3 185
<i>Atriplex nummularia</i>	1 688	42	235 063	5 824
<i>Biancaea decapetala</i>	803 978	15 852	332 000	8 774
<i>Cereus jamacaru</i>	435 255	13 588	839 175	10 899
<i>Cestrum</i> spp.	1 019	59	127 613	7 138
<i>Chromolaena odorata</i>	290 323	22 541	1 489 919	101 168
<i>Eucalyptus</i> spp.	1 486 217	38 038	6 103 288	271 042
<i>Hakea</i> spp.	570 656	36 600	327 706	35 865
<i>Jacaranda mimosifolia</i>	1 263 946	19 213	277 738	4 186
<i>Lantana camara</i>	1 324 950	40 578	571 919	31 959
<i>Melia azedarach</i>	2 035 991	48 287	1 664 750	14 157
<i>Opuntia</i> spp.	1 531 806	66 717	3 422 575	94 498
<i>Pinus</i> spp.	2 191 471	53 354	3 362 606	130 608
<i>Populus</i> spp.	861 150	8 872	2 381 438	57 722
<i>Prosopis</i> spp.	60 306	1 096	262 244	5 182
<i>Psidium guajava</i>	421 395	13 314	303 031	6 205
<i>Rosa rubiginosa</i>	0	0	408 956	11 674
<i>Salix babylonica</i>	75 142	6 357	2 337 200	37 296
<i>Senna didymobotrya</i>	22 150	519	454 581	11 451
<i>Sesbania punicea</i>	777 149	12 989	48 756	40 011
<i>Solanum mauritianum</i>	1 015 063	37 884	1 091 238	1 663
<i>Tamarix chinensis</i>	2 112	412	88 006	2 116

The exclusion of low-density invasions by *Acacia cyclops* makes almost no difference (Suppl. Table 3.2.2), perhaps because it is quite easily distinguished from the air. However, the same does not apply to *Acacia mearnsii*, where the exclusion of invasions <5% density makes a large difference in the total invaded area and the same applies to *Acacia saligna*. Both species should be easily distinguishable, so the actual detectability of the plants should not

be a major issue. In the case of *A. saligna*, exclusion of densities <5% brings the data much more in line with the NIAPS estimates. In the case of eucalypts though, the exclusion of low-density areas simply increases the discrepancy.

Suppl. Table 3.2.2 An assessment of the impacts of excluding low-density invasions on species in the Versfeld dataset for the area where the surveys overlapped.

Species	Without Rare (ha)		Excluding $\leq 1\%$ density (ha)		Excluding <5% density (ha)	
	Condensed	Total	Condensed	Total	Condensed	Total
<i>Acacia cyclops</i>	269 568	1 253 802	269 157	1 171 489	266 501	1 066 390
<i>Acacia dealbata</i>	42 188	489 484	41 975	468 166	26 391	361 961
<i>Acacia decurrens</i>	2 301	36 891	2 028	9 590	2 026	9 505
<i>Acacia mearnsii</i>	87 165	1 238 353	86 379	1 105 372	64 115	244 070
<i>Acacia saligna</i>	73 159	1 034 410	73 070	1 016 232	56 168	354 537
<i>Acacia spp.</i>	32 942	111 935	28 154	80 578	31 694	77 691
<i>Eucalyptus spp.</i>	35 332	795 568	33 961	605 445	20 800	82 264
<i>Lantana camara</i>	40 577	1 314 678	40 161	1 273 115	8 688	39 234
<i>Pinus halepensis</i>	205	674	205	674	201	544
<i>Pinus patula</i>	1 953	59 928	1 560	20 603	1 319	10 948
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	36 574	662 465	35 133	360 952	29 437	149 380
<i>Pinus radiata</i>	5 326	150 398	5 014	76 275	3 161	8 648
<i>Pinus spp.</i>	9 024	127 032	9 093	114 496	7 024	35 809
<i>Populus canescens</i>	2 660	50 293	2 245	7 941	2 129	3 527
<i>Populus deltoides</i>	370	24 412	131	4 963	128	385
<i>Populus spp.</i>	5 501	141 843	5 583	135 421	2 224	5 885
<i>Salix babylonica</i>	4 095	56 737	4 039	49 007	2 478	9 776
<i>Salix spp.</i>	2 262	18 473	2 262	18 473	2 098	11 929

This comparison of the surveys shows that the differences in the mapping approaches and the coverage of the two surveys are such that the data cannot be meaningfully compared. The Versfeld dataset included areas mapped at a very fine scale for management plans (e.g. Upper Sabie, Keurbooms, Riviersonderend) at the tertiary catchment level which is about the minimum spatial unit for interpreting the NIAPS data (Kotzé et al., 2010) so comparisons of the two datasets at this level are to be interpreted with caution.

A comparison between the Versfeld and the NIAPS data for the Riviersonderend catchment (tertiary H60) in the Western Cape shows some marked differences, notably that the NIAPS recorded less than half the total condensed invaded area in the 11 quaternary catchments (Suppl. Table 3.2.3). Only four taxa were recorded by the NIAPS compared with 31 mapped for the management plan (Gelderblom et al., 1997). The total condensed area of all 32 species came to 19 072 ha. These differences can be seen in all the taxa except for *Hakea* species. The NIAPS data are for the landscape invasions which did not specifically sample riparian areas and this may explain the underestimation of the *Eucalyptus* and *Acacia mearnsii* invasions which are largely limited to the floodplain. However this cannot explain the differences in the invasions of *Pinus* species.

Suppl. Table 3.2.3 A comparison of the invasions mapped for the Riviersonderend catchment (tertiary H60)

Taxon	Versfeld (condensed ha)	NIAPS 2007 (condensed ha)
<i>Acacia mearnsii</i>	3 666	457
<i>Eucalyptus</i>	2 672	377
<i>Hakea</i>	1 906	1 895
<i>Pinus</i>	8 818	4 788
Total condensed ha	17 062	7 517
Total mapped ha	91 091	118 031

A similar comparison of the data for the Upper Wilge river catchment in the Highveld grasslands of Free State, Mpumalanga and Gauteng (Bailey et al., 1997) also shows marked differences but in this case they are reversed with a far greater condensed area being recorded by the NIAPS (Suppl. Table 3.2.4). In this case, most of the taxa recorded by the NIAPS are primarily riparian invaders so the use of the landscape invasion data cannot explain the differences. One difference for *Eucalyptus* is that the Highveld is characterised by numerous *Eucalyptus* woodlots which were not captured in the Versfeld summaries but were included in the original field mapping as woodlots.

Suppl. Table 3.2.4 A comparison of the invasions mapped for the Upper Wilge River catchment (tertiary C81)

Taxon	Versfeld (condensed ha)	NIAPS 2007 (condensed ha)
<i>Acacia mearnsii</i>	2 524	8 348
<i>Eucalyptus</i>	2 306	6 392
<i>Pinus</i>	424	762
<i>Populus</i>	292	3 340
<i>Salix</i>	707	1 441
Total condensed area (ha)	6 623	20 283
Total invaded area (ha)	11 771	482 106

A comparison of the invasions in the Keurbooms River system also found that the Versfeld invasions were more extensive than the NIAPS, whereas the more detailed mapping done for the Garden Route Initiative (Holness and Bradshaw, 2010) was much higher, suggesting that the NIAPS did underestimate the invasions in this catchment as well (Suppl. Table 3.2.5). Unfortunately, because plantation areas were excluded from the NIAPS mapping we were not able to compare data from the invasions mapped for the Sabie Catchment Management Plan. Most of the invasions were riparian but the 250 x 250 m resolution of the NIAPS data meant that most of the riparian areas were classified as plantations.

Suppl. Table 3.2.5 A comparison of the invasions mapped for the Keurbooms River catchment (tertiary K60) (DC Le Maitre, unpubl data)

Study	Versfeld (condensed ha)	NIAPS (condensed ha)	Garden Route Initiative (condensed ha)
Pines	8 539	4 443	10 364
All acacias	3 803	3 812	7 294

These results could be interpreted as indicating that invasions in fynbos catchments have been underestimated by the NIAPS, and that those in the grasslands were underestimated

by Versfeld, but the data are too limited to support this type of generalisation except where the Versfeld mapping was poor.

Overall, the NIAPS provides a more consistent and even coverage of the wetter regions of the country than Versfeld, especially the invasions in the Eastern Cape, but needs to be extended to the drier regions of the country.

References

- Bailey C, Gelderblom C, Le Maitre D, Evans J, Chapman A, van Wilgen B, Vink D, Muller J, Savrada D, Brown P (1997). Management plan for the Upper Wilge River Catchment. CSIR Report, CSIR, Stellenbosch
- Gelderblom C, Le Maitre D, McKelly D, van der Heyden F, Chapman A, van Wilgen B, Robyntjies R, Carelse L, van Wyk E, Burns K, Rowlinson L, Sulaiman A (1997) Management plan for alien vegetation in the Riviersonderend Catchment. A. Main report. B. Appendices
- Holness S, Bradshaw P (2010) Critical Biodiversity Areas of the Overberg District Municipality. Conservation Planning Report Park Planning and Development Unit, South African National Parks
- Impson FAC, Kleinjan CA, Hoffmann JH, Post JA (2008) *Dasineura rubiformis* (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae), a new biological control agent for *Acacia mearnsii* in South Africa. *S Afr J Sci* 104: 247–249
- Kotzé I, Beukes H, van den Berg E, Newby T (2010) National Invasive Alien Plant Survey. Report No. GW/A/2010/21, Agricultural Research Council – Institute for Soil, Climate and Water, Pretoria
- Le Maitre DC, Forsyth GG, Dziki S, Gush MB (2013) Estimates of the impacts of invasive alien plants on water flows in South Africa. Report No. CSIR/NRE/ECO/ER/2013/0067/B, Natural Resources and the Environment, CSIR, Stellenbosch
- van Wilgen BW, Forsyth GG, Le Maitre DC, Wannenburg A, Kotzé JDF, van den Berg E, Henderson L (2012) An assessment of the effectiveness of a large, national-scale invasive alien plant control strategy in South Africa. *Biol Conserv* 148: 28–38

van Wilgen BW, Wilson JRU, Faulkner K, Morapi T, Mnikathi Z, Munyai T, Rahlao S (2017) The status of biological invasions and their management in South Africa in 2017. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Kirstenbosch and DST-NRF Centre of Excellence for Invasion Biology, Stellenbosch

Versfeld DB, Le Maitre DC, Chapman RA (1998) Alien invading plants and water resources in South Africa: a preliminary assessment. Report No. TT99/98, Water Research Commission, Pretoria

Supplementary Appendix 3.3. Approach for defining alien plant species assemblage zones

The Simpson Dissimilarity Index was computed for all pairs of QDGCs with more than 5 alien species to compare species composition (including QDGCs with less than five species led to biases in the comparisons of QDGCs and prevent the NMDS algorithm to generate sensible results). Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) was then applied to the resulting distance matrix, and each cell was assigned a set of coordinates in a three-dimensional space. All points were then translated in the space so that they would fall in a cube with unit-length edge, using the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned}x_i' &= (x_i + \min(x)) \\y_i' &= (y_i + \min(y)) \\z_i' &= (z_i + \min(z))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}x_i'' &= \frac{x_i'}{\max(x', y', z')} \\y_i'' &= \frac{y_i'}{\max(x', y', z')} \\z_i'' &= \frac{z_i'}{\max(x', y', z')}\end{aligned}$$

where x_i , y_i , and z_i are the coordinates of QDGCs resulting from the NMDS. These two successive transformations ensure that the distances between QDGCs in three-dimensional space remain proportional to each other. These coordinates were then interpreted as RGB colours to allow for the visualization of differences in species composition between QDGCs (Ferrier et al. 2007). Each QDGC is therefore characterised by a specific colour (R,G,B), relative to all other QDGCs, and QDGCs with similar colours (which are close to each other in the three-dimensional RGB space) have similar species composition (Suppl. Fig. 3.3.1 (top)).

Suppl. Fig. 3.3.1. TOP: Each quarter-degree grid cell (QDGC) is attributed a colour based on its coordinate in a three-dimensional RGB space resulting from applying non-metric dimensional scaling to the Simpson Dissimilarity Index between pairs of QDGCs. QDGCs with similar colours have similar species composition. BOTTOM: The four alien plant species assemblage zones identified using a K-means algorithm. The colours correspond to the

coordinates of the centroid of each zone and their difference represents the compositional dissimilarity between the zones.

Although the species composition of QDGCs changes gradually in space, classifying QDGCs into discrete clusters (zones) offers a more straightforward ecological perspective on the spatial distribution of alien species assemblages. A K-means clustering algorithm was then used on the QDS based on their location in the three-dimensional space to identify clusters of cells based on their species composition. The appropriate number of zones was determined by comparing 30 criteria, using the function NbClust() from the NbClust package in R. Amongst the 30 criteria, the consensus was four zones. The coordinates of each of the four zones' centroids was determined in the RGB space, and the corresponding colours were attributed to QDGCs based on the zone to which they belonged (Suppl. Fig. 3.3.1 (bottom)). The colours of each zone also indicates similarity or difference between the zones. Here, the four zones have very different colours, and are equally distant from each other in the RGB space (Suppl. Table 3.3.1).

Suppl. Table 3.3.1 Distance between zone centroids in the RGB space.

	A	B	C
B	0.2946817		
C	0.2919091	0.3059912	
D	0.3171418	0.2844883	0.2925564

References

Ferrier S, Manion G, Elith J, Richardson K (2007) Using generalized dissimilarity modelling to analyse and predict patterns of beta diversity in regional biodiversity assessment. *Divers Distrib* 13: 252-264

Supplementary Appendix 3.4 Methods for exploring the relationship between species richness of naturalised alien and native plants in quarter-degree grid cells and environmental variables

The relationship between richness and the different environmental variables was computed using Boosted Regression Trees (BRTs). BRTs fit a large number of simple regression trees and combine them in a single model (Thuiller et al. 2006). Nine variables representing five different hypotheses on drivers of species richness were used (as in the Table below).

Hypothesis variable	Description
Topographic heterogeneity	
CV_ALTI	Coefficient of variation of altitude
Favourableness	
MAP	Mean annual precipitation
SWSMIN_MEA	Mean soil water stress
GTEMP	Mean Growing temperature (Mean Growing Degree Day above 10 degrees?)
MTCOLD	Mean temperature Coldest Month
Energy	
MTEMP_MEAN	Mean annual temperature
PRODUCTIVITY	Mean productivity
Irregularity	
CV_RAIN	CV rainfall
Human influence	
dat.hi	Index of human influence

Because of high levels of correlations between some variables, we used the residuals of linear regressions for some variables to ensure that correlations were < 0.6 . GTEMP and MTCOLD were regressed against MTEMP_MEAN; CV_RAIN, PRODUCTIVITY and dat.hi were regressed against MAP. All correlations are then < 0.6 or > -0.6 .

BRTs were then computed for the whole of South Africa, for each native biome and for each alien plant species assemblage zones (see Supplementary Appendix 3.1), using tree sizes of 2 and a Poisson distribution, following Thuiller et al. (2006). BRTs were computed using the `dismo` package (Elith and Leathwick 2017) for R. A 10-fold cross-validation procedure (the default in the `gbm.step` R function) was used to parameterize the BRTs, and the correlation between BRT predictions and observed data is reported for the validation data as a measure of performance.

References

Thuiller WF, Midgley G, Rouget M, Cowling RM (2006) Predicting patterns of plant species richness in megadiverse South Africa. *Ecography* 29: 733-744

Elith J, Leathwick J (2017) Boosted Regression Trees for ecological modeling. R documentation. Available at <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/dismo/vignettes/brt.pdf>